

Machine Learning Methods Towards Analog mm-Wave Systems

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ABSTRACT

We hereby outline a state-of-the-art survey on the applications of machine learning in analog Radio over Fiber systems. An overview of recent implementations towards an improved physical layer performance is presented.

Keywords: Analog Systems, Analog Radio over Fiber, Millimetre Wave Communication, Machine Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Analog Radio Over Fiber (ARoF) is a potential candidate for future C-RAN aiming to offer novel spectrum opportunities compared to the Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI)-based digital Radio over Fiber (DRoF), which shows spectral inefficiency due to high resolution quantization [1]. ARoF mm-Wave (MMW) systems incorporate nonlinear signal distortions due to intrinsic limitations of RF photonics. In particular, Mach Zehnder Modulator (MZM) produces spectral regrowth effect [2], while fiber linear chromatic dispersion (CD) and nonlinear effects introduce carrier fading, undesired harmonics and nonlinear cross modulation (XM) effects in multi-user single-carrier frequency division multiple access (SC-FDMA) and orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) schemes [3]-[4]. As physical layer impairment mitigation technique, machine learning (ML) is in focus: allowing simultaneous impairments mitigation when used in digital pre-distorters (DPD) or post equalizers (PE). We hereby outline recent state-of-the-art (SOTA) applications of ML aiming at the mitigation of the abovementioned impairments in ARoF, with a particular focus on MMW implementations.

2. MACHINE LEARNING BASED EQUALIZERS

Fig 1. DPD and PE options for MMW ARoF systems. The right inset summarizes the PE options from literature.

DSP-based MMW systems depicted in Fig 1 comprise an RF transmitter (*i.e.*, data modulator), serving as input for a DPD where ML models are utilized. DPD aims to pre-distort the signal prior to transmission. It is trained to learn the system inverse cascade response (*i.e.*, *input-output nonlinear relationships*) and after converging, independently associate new input instances to their appropriate labels. As the modulated optical signal propagates through the fiber it may suffer from several effects before it reaches the receiver DSP block where ML PE may be implemented. A PE may be realized using various artificial neural network (ANN) architectures, such as multi-layer perceptron (MLP) [2], [4], [5], recurrent neural networks (RNN) [6], and long short term memory neural network (LSTM-NN) [1]. Similarly, DPD-ANNs in the form of nonlinear waveform regression are realized in MLPs [2], as well as RNNs [6], [7].

A MLP-NN, where the MZM non linearities were considered memoryless, was proposed and assessed in DPD and PE to improve the error vector magnitude (EVM) from 10% to below 3% for 16QAM at 20dB RF power while maintaining the NN complexity low [2]. To address the effects with memory, (*i.e.*, the power amplifier non linearities) and to simultaneously reduce in-band and out-band distortions caused by MZM, an RNN-DPD and a PE were proposed in [6], showing that RNN outperforms MLP in such scenario when RNN memory depth is equal to or higher than the PA memory depth. However, the proposed schemes were not able to enhance the EVM of 16QAM below the 3GPP threshold. An extension to prior research was performed, taking into account the CD effect and proposing a time delay line MLP-DPD architecture instead of RNN to compensate for both linear and nonlinear effects [8], achieving an EVM reduction from 12% to 3% for 16QAM at 20dB RF power. In [7], an optimization of RNN-DPD hyperparameters was carried out to further reduce the EVM of 5G NR waveform from 12% to 1.65%, below the 3GPP standardized EVM for 256QAM. Furthermore, to overcome the vanishing and exploding gradients in RNN, the use of LSTM was proposed in [1]. With the aid of a reference tone, a LSTM-PE based receiver improved the phase noise tolerance in oscillator based down-converted heterodyned ARoF, achieving BER improvement from 10^{-1} to a BER of 10^{-5} . Fig 1(a, b) illustrates the MLP-PE architectures [3]-[4] used in mitigating the cross-modulation (XM) distortion. A complex-valued multi-level sigmoid function was utilized to achieve joint equalization for 4 users in [3]. In [4], time-domain real valued training was leveraged to overcome the limitations of complex-valued MLP towards addressing the phase noise, and achieved a 1.5 dB receiver sensitivity improvement. To reduce the training cost, transfer learning approach

and an adaptive activation function were proposed in [4], [5]. Finally, conventional maximum likelihood can be replaced by ML classifiers for signal decision to offer an effective BER reduction when the signal suffers from nonlinearities. Support vector machine (SVM) classifier aims to find the best boundary (hyperplane) to distinguish between classes. In [9], eight SVMs were used in the classification task for 256QAM, achieving BER improvement from 10^{-4} to 10^{-5} .

A summary of recently implemented ML techniques is reported in Table 1, highlighting the following research gaps. The application of ML-based impairment mitigation in MMW ARoF systems ($f_{RF} > 30\text{GHz}$) reported in recent literature is mostly based on MLP-NN. Moreover, we note insufficient focus on MMW frequencies beyond 60GHz. The typically implemented delayed time line-MLP architectures, aiming at CD compensation and MZM/PA linearization, require high neuron count in each layer leading to increased complexity. Finally, it is of note that PD-induced distortion compensation is not considered in [2], [6], and [8].

Table 1. Recent ML implementation, where “-” indicates that data are not being provided

Year/Ref.	f_{RF}	Fig.1	ML Type	Neuron/Layer Count	Reach, ODN/ Wireless
2022[2]	-	ii-b	MLP-NN	2,32,16,2	- / -
2023[6]	-	ii-b	RNN	2,64,32,2	- / -
2023[8]	-	ii-c	MLP-NN	18,1024,1024,1024,2	- / -
2024[7]	10GHz	ii-c	RNN	2, -, -, 2	10km SMF / -
2022[1]	60GHz	i--	LSTM-NN	-	-
2018[3]	60GHz	i-a	MLP-NN	5,24,1	15km SMF / 0.8m
2023[4]	-	i-b	MLP-NN	1,8,16,32,64,16,8,1	2km MCF / -
2017[5]	60GHz	i-a	MLP-NN	12,16,1	10km SMF / 1.2m
2019[9]	-	-	SVM	- (8 SVMs)	50km SMF / -

3. CONCLUSIONS

We present an overview of recent ML implementations aiming at mitigation of physical layer impairments in ARoF systems, and identify related research gaps. We outlined recent ANN architectures under different hyperparameters to track the MZM memoryless effect, PA memory effect, CD and cross modulation in multi-user SC-FDMA and OFDM converged wireless optical networks.

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